

Review article

Optimizing NZEB performance: A review of design strategies and case studies

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ABSTRACT

The world confronts significant energy issues, propelled by increasing energy consumption in buildings and escalating apprehensions regarding carbon emissions from the industry. Inefficient building practices exacerbate energy instability, especially in areas experiencing increased urbanization. Nearly-zero Energy Buildings (NZEBs) present an effective remedy to these challenges, markedly decreasing energy usage and carbon emissions while fostering sustainability.

This research thoroughly assesses the development of NZEBs from 1995 to 2024, emphasizing design concepts, technological innovations, and their impact on energy efficiency. An analysis of key impediments to implementation reveals high prices, limited technological feasibility, regulatory limitations, and insufficient stakeholder participation. The paper examines the revolutionary impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on enhancing NZEB performance, highlighting applications such as predictive energy analytics, intelligent HVAC systems, and real-time energy management. Focusing on Egypt within the larger MENA region, this article emphasizes the unique difficulties faced by the country due to its varied climates and different stages of regulatory development. The research delineates region-specific ways to surmount challenges, including the integration of sophisticated renewable energy systems, the optimization of building envelopes, and the promotion of multi-stakeholder engagement.

The results highlight the necessity for customized solutions and improved regional and worldwide cooperation to expedite the implementation of NZEBs, fostering a sustainable and resilient built environment. This analysis offers practical insights for researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders aiming to promote NZEB adoption in the MENA area and beyond.

1. Introduction

The world is now more chaotic and unpredictable than ever in history. Our fears about the future determine the present. People must prepare for future difficulties if humanity desires to live in a secure world. By only taking action, people can improve the planet in the future and in the present [1].

Climate change is occurring, and decisive action is needed to avert its

catastrophic implications [2]. Failure to take action now to control greenhouse gas emissions, according to the Climate Change Intergovernmental Panel, will result in expensive risks to mankind, the economy, and the environment. Water scarcity and extensive drought are among the threats, as are increasingly extreme weather events, rising sea levels and storm surges, lower agricultural yields in already susceptible areas, the loss of various species of animals and plants, and higher health hazards in many regions [3,4]. The latest edition of the IEA's World

Abbreviations: ABs, Autonomous Buildings; AIoT, Artificial Intelligence of Things; BPS, Building Performance Simulation; EPBD, Energy Performance Building Directive; EUI, Energy Usage Intensity; FCU, Fan Coil Units; GHG, Greenhouse Gas; GBs, Green Buildings; HVAC, Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning; IEQ, Indoor Environmental Quality; LS, Lighting system; MENA, Middle East and North Africa; NREL, National Renewable Energy Laboratory; NZEB, Nearly Zero Energy Building; PV, Photovoltaics.

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Energy Outlook reveals that the global energy challenges arising from the conflict between Russia and Ukraine are causing significant and long-lasting changes. These changes have the potential to expedite the shift towards a more environmentally sustainable and secure energy system [5].

Moreover, the significant increase in the global population since 1950 can be attributed to two factors: firstly, the gradual increase in the average lifespan of individuals due to significant advancements in health care, food production, personal cleanliness, and medical treatments; and secondly, the continued prevalence of high fertility rates in numerous countries. Consequently, the global population has increased by more than four times since the mid-20th century, surpassing 8 billion individuals in 2022. Based on United Nations projections, the global population is expected to potentially reach approximately 11 billion by the year 2100 [6,7]. So it is predicted that by 2060, worldwide building floor area will quadruple. To handle the most remarkable surge of urban expansion in the history of humankind, it is planned to add 2.4 trillion ft² (230 billion m²) of additional floor space to the global building stock per month for the next 40 years, the equivalent of adding an additional New York City to the world [8]. So, buildings have a crucial role in energy usage and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions throughout their lifespan, both directly (through operation) and indirectly (through the manufacturing of construction materials, building processes, transportation, restoration, and destruction). At the same time, these effects emphasize the necessity of using a dynamic approach in life cycle evaluations [9].

Moreover, buildings account for 40% of global energy usage and contribute 30% of total CO₂ emissions. Consequently, buildings' energy efficiency is now a primary concern for policymakers since the building sector ranks among the most energy-intensive industries [10,11]. In the MENA region, where construction activity is on the rise, it is imperative to establish and enforce energy efficiency regulations for new buildings in order to reduce energy consumption. In the last 30 years, primary energy consumption in the region has increased markedly, with an annual growth rate of 8% during the past decade. Buildings constitute more than 74% of the region's electricity usage, with the residential sector at 45.6%, the tertiary sector at 28.7%, and the industrial sector at 23.2%. Over the course of a building's 40–50-year lifespan, or even longer, energy-efficient designs can significantly cut down on energy use and emissions of greenhouse gases. Numerous MENA nations have implemented energy efficiency regulations, standards, and labeling for buildings and appliances, focusing on refrigerators, cooling systems, and lights. Nonetheless, the execution and enforcement of these policies continue to be variable throughout the region [12–14].

As climate change, energy, the economy, and buildings have intricate and interconnected relationships, the building industry is accountable for considerable global energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. With the world's population continuously growing and urbanizing, energy consumption in buildings is projected to increase significantly. Accordingly, climate change is accelerating with increasing global temperatures and frequent extreme weather events, worsening the cooling and heating energy demands of buildings. The amplified energy demands may lead to higher energy expenses and economic instability, ultimately affecting the economy negatively. As a result, building design, architecture, and operations are critical to tackling climate change and maintaining energy security while encouraging economic growth. This highlights the importance of promoting energy-efficient buildings and transitioning to low-carbon energy sources to decrease greenhouse gas emissions, combat climate change, and guarantee economic prosperity [15–20].

Considering the present environmental and economic concerns, the need for green buildings is quite significant. As nations work to address climate change, enhance energy efficiency, and promote sustainable development, the need for green buildings is becoming more apparent. These buildings provide pragmatic solutions to these interrelated challenges, showcasing their significance in tackling current global

problems. According to the International Green Building Council, green buildings are those that, by their design, construction, or operations, minimize or eliminate the adverse effects on the climate and natural environment even while having the potential to bring beneficial effects [21,22]. According to the Energy Performance Building Directive EPBD, Nearly Zero Energy Building (NZEB) is one of the top sustainable building methods utilized today in green building practices, and energy demands are generated on-site utilizing renewable energy [23].

NZEBs present a pivotal opportunity to markedly decrease energy consumption in buildings while guaranteeing enhanced thermal comfort and reducing environmental impact. The NZEB idea emphasizes the construction of highly efficient structures with reduced energy needs, where a significant fraction of energy demand is satisfied through renewable energy sources, whether on-site or off-site [24].

However, the transition to NZEBs confronts numerous significant challenges that must be solved to enable practical, long-term, and effective implementation. Critical concerns encompass attaining an ideal equilibrium between energy efficiency and the incorporation of renewable energy, addressing local and temporal energy fluctuations, and establishing suitable energy performance standards. Further complexity emerges from integrating other energy consumption parameters, including indoor power usage, the lifetime effects of building and disposal, and the practicality of collective energy evaluations. By confronting these obstacles through thorough assessment and strategic planning, policymakers and industry stakeholders may facilitate the successful implementation of NZEBs, enhancing a more sustainable and energy-efficient built environment [25].

This review study seeks to deliver a thorough review of sustainable and energy-efficient building approaches, concentrating on Egypt's specific climatic and energy-related difficulties. Despite being a well-established concept, the practical implementation and adaptation of NZEBs to Egypt's unique development are still not widely recognized. This article employs a comprehensive approach by synthesizing global perspectives on climate change and energy use with Egypt's unique vulnerabilities and prospects. The evaluation emphasizes the potential of emerging technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), for enhancing building performance in alignment with NZEB objectives, energy storage and generating systems, as well as existing tactics such as envelope design and HVAC optimization. This study synthesizes interconnected topics to offer new insights specific to Egypt, with the objective of guiding future research, informing the development of policies, and promoting sustainable building techniques to successfully tackle environmental and energy concerns.

1.1. Scope and approach

This paper intends to provide an extensive review of nearly-zero Energy Buildings and the methodologies used to design, construct, and operate them. To achieve this aim, a systematic literature review was conducted using a three-step approach, as shown in Fig. 1.

Step 1: Identification of Relevant Studies

The initial phase entailed selecting pertinent studies through extensive searches across various academic databases, such as Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Science Direct. Terms such as “net-zero Energy Buildings,” “energy-efficient buildings,” “sustainable buildings,” “carbon emissions,” “building envelope,” “HVAC systems,” and “renewable energy systems” were employed to encompass a broad spectrum of studies pertinent to NZEB research. The search was confined to articles from 1995 to 2024 to incorporate both seminal studies and recent developments in NZEB technologies.

Step 2: Screening and Selection of Studies

During this step, full-text publications were assessed for relevance according to established inclusion criteria. Emphasis was placed on research pertaining to the design, construction, operation, and performance of nearly-zero Energy Buildings (NZEBs), along with comparative evaluations between NZEBs and conventional buildings. Focus was

Fig. 1. Research methodology.

directed toward papers concerning essential elements such as building envelope design, HVAC system optimization, and the use of renewable energy technology. Publications were omitted for insufficient methodological rigor or absence of relevant data corresponding to the scope and aims of this review.

Step 3: Retrieval and Synthesis of Data

The last phase was the retrieval and synthesis of data. The retrieved data were synthesized and analyzed using a narrative technique to uncover common themes, noteworthy results, and research gaps.

As shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the values given in the chart about the number of references utilized in this paper denote the diversity of sources consulted. The presence of 139 journal articles indicates a reliance on peer-reviewed literature for primary research sources. Furthermore, 47 report references suggest supplementing primary

sources with government and organizational reports. Including 14 conference references implies either the presentation of the research at a conference or the usage of conference proceedings. Finally, the inclusion of 11 book references. The values offer valuable insight into the sources in this review paper, facilitating a more thorough evaluation of the research’s quality and validity.

1.1.1. References statistics visualization

Visualizing reference data is an essential tool for researchers to assess the frequency and distribution of keywords and authors within a particular research topic.

In this paper, VOS software 1.6.20 version [26] is used to build overlay visualizations that display the co-occurrence of authors and keywords in a network, as shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Fig. 2. Number of references used per year.

Fig. 3. References statistics.

The software creates a network using bibliographic data, with nodes representing keywords or authors and edges representing the co-occurrence of those nodes in the same publication. The thickness of the edges denotes the strength of the co-occurrence, while the nodes' size and color show the occurrence frequency. Visualizations give researchers a clear view of the structure and links between various keywords and authors in their field of study, allowing them to discover emerging trends, critical research gaps, and possible partners.

The overlay visualization in Figs. 4 and 5 accurately depicts the collaborative networks among authors and keywords obtained from references, respectively. The document-based author collaboration network is shown in Fig. 4, which captures many aspects like the strength of the collaboration and the frequency of co-authorship. With authors as nodes and their relationships as links, this framework incorporates authors who have contributed to at least one document. This visualization technique provides useful insights into the intricate processes of collaboration within research communities.

In addition to that, Fig. 5 shows a keyword overlay visualization

based on the references listed in this review, demonstrating the core themes and their interconnections within the NZEB research domain. This visualization, generated with VOSviewer, emphasizes essential terms such as thermal comfort, energy efficiency, carbon dioxide emissions, and renewable energy, which are pivotal to the literature on NZEB. The color scheme of the nodes indicates publication years, with older works depicted in darker hues (e.g., purple and blue) and more recent research in lighter tones (e.g., yellow and green). Recent years have seen an increase in the prominence of keywords such as energy efficiency, artificial intelligence, and design thinking, while core issues like thermal insulation and indoor environmental quality are represented in deeper hues, signifying their established significance in the discipline. Keyword clusters, such as the relationship between thermal insulation and nearly zero Energy Buildings, underscore current research on building performance and comfort. The connections between renewable energy and power generation illustrate the growing emphasis on incorporating sustainable energy solutions in NZEB architecture. This illustration offers a comprehensive overview of the evolving patterns and principal study domains in NZEB studies, delivering significant insights into the field's progression throughout time.

Furthermore, a geolocation map, illustrated in Fig. 6, has been developed to offer a more precise depiction of the contributions to this review paper on NZEB. This map illustrates the author's affiliations and depicts the distribution of contributions among various nations. Fig. 7 demonstrates that Egypt is the leading contributor at 17%, closely followed by the USA at 14%. China and Italy also provide substantial contributions. The percentages derived from the provided references in the research elucidate the specific aim of implementing NZEB technology, particularly in Egypt, while emphasizing the essential role of global collaboration in advancing NZEB technology. This geolocation-oriented viewpoint emphasizes the interrelation of worldwide initiatives to promote NZEB technologies. The emphasis on Egypt arises from the review's scope, while the data underscores the need for coordinated strategies to expedite NZEB implementation and advance sustainable building practices globally.

Fig. 4. Author collaboration network using VOS viewer.

Fig. 5. Largest set of connected key words overlay visualization using VOS viewer.

Fig. 6. Geolocation visualization of references.

2. Literature Review

As a major contributor to both global energy consumption and emissions, the building sector must play a pivotal role in finding solutions to the energy crisis and climate change. Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEBS) have arisen as a pivotal option, seeking to reduce energy use and incorporate renewable energy sources. This section analyzes the relationship among climate change, energy consumption, and

building sustainability, emphasizing worldwide trends and the particular issues faced by Egypt. This section subsequently examines energy-efficient strategies, which include NZEBs, sustainable building practices, and the impact of emerging technology such as artificial intelligence on enhancing building efficiency.

Fig. 7. References distribution by country.

2.1. Climate Change Phenomena

Globally observed and predicted climate trends for the twenty-first century, as well as global warming, have been significant changes during the previous 65 years. Climate change is an interconnected worldwide issue that affects various ecological, environmental, sociopolitical, and economic fields [27]. The world's temperatures are increasing due to climate change [28]. The worldwide climate crisis escalated significantly with the onset of the modern era [29]. According to reports, immediate attention and appropriate procedures may boost the likelihood of overcoming its catastrophic effects. The exact impacts of climate change cannot be predicted on a sectoral basis [30]. This is demonstrated by the growing level of awareness and the integration of climate uncertainty regulations at the local and federal levels [31].

Climate change is determined by persistent alterations in the amount of precipitation, temperature, and other environmental factors such as pressure and humidity over an extended period of time. Furthermore, notable worldwide and regional impacts of climate change encompass erratic weather phenomena, the global retreat of glaciers, and the resulting rise in sea levels [32].

In Africa, based on the Emissions Gap Report 2022, 2021 was the third or fourth hottest year on record. Moreover, it is estimated that by 2030, 108–116 million Africans will be at risk of sea-level rise. Furthermore, drought in East Africa has deteriorated due to multiple failed wet seasons, increased violence, population relocation, and COVID-19 limitations [33].

Comparably, the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region faces serious threats to ecosystems and human activities, making it one of the most sensitive regions in the world to the effects of climate change. The region, characterized by severe water scarcity and arid circumstances, depends significantly on climate-sensitive agriculture and has substantial populations and economic activity centered in flood-prone coastal metropolitan regions. Chronic hazards, including droughts, heatwaves, and extreme weather events, intensify these issues, endangering the region's sustainability and resilience [34,35].

Amid the MENA region, Egypt stands out for its diverse range of climates, from coastal areas affected by the Mediterranean to hyper-arid deserts. This climatic variability presents a complicated set of issues, as

each region displays unique susceptibilities to climate change, requiring highly tailored adaptation and mitigation techniques [36]. Compounding these issues is Egypt's dependency on the Nile River, which provides over 95% of the nation's freshwater, alongside its significant reliance on agriculture and energy-intensive systems, all of which are highly susceptible to climatic variations [37]. The interconnected vulnerabilities and resource dependencies highlight Egypt's importance as a critical case study for developing customized climate resilience solutions, which may be applicable to other countries in the region experiencing similar climatic and socio-economic challenges.

2.1.1. Climate Change in Egypt

Egypt has surpassed the globally acknowledged water shortage threshold and is on the verge of "absolute water scarcity" as temperatures in the MENA region rise. Desertification (land deterioration in water-stressed areas of the world) is predicted to impact 3.5 feddans (3.6 acres) of land in Egypt per hour. With less than 3% of Egypt's land being suitable for farming, the alarming pace of desertification poses a significant threat of drought and diminishes the productivity of agricultural land. Consequently, the well-being of underprivileged populations in Egypt, as well as overall food security, is at risk. Therefore, it is crucial to address Egypt's heightened susceptibility to climate change and mitigate its adverse impacts to ensure the nation's sustained economic well-being [38,39].

The climate-related challenges faced by impoverished Egyptians can be attributed to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In 2018, Egypt was ranked 28th among 193 nations, contributing 0.67% of the total yearly carbon dioxide emissions, which amounts to 329.4 million tons. Currently, 91% of the country's electrical output is derived from fossil fuels [40]. In order to achieve the goals, set out in the 2015 Paris Climate Agreement, it is necessary for governments to make more significant and dedicated efforts towards reducing carbon emissions [38].

2.1.2. Buildings and Environment

Although people's understanding of climate change is growing, many are still unaware of how climate change affects energy use in buildings. Building activities account for 28% of overall emissions, whereas embodied carbon from construction and building materials

accounts for 11%. This accounts for roughly 40% of CO₂ emissions from the construction and building sectors, accounting for more than 33% of worldwide energy use [41].

Studies conducted at Cambridge University suggest climate change is likely to have substantial consequences for the built environment. However, the precise magnitude of these effects remains uncertain and is subject to considerable variation within and between different regions. Many buildings are susceptible to climate change, increasing their vulnerability to catastrophic disasters [42].

An Australian study has found that climate change has various notable consequences for buildings. These include heightened energy consumption as temperatures rise, health risks linked to overheating, more frequent tropical hurricanes and storms, a greater likelihood of serious damage to foundations and pipelines during windy weather, soil depletion, cracks, and earth disruptions, increased flood damage, and a higher risk of forestry fires [43].

Furthermore, a review paper from Qatar states that climate change would modify the requirements for building energy usage and building energy infrastructure, including distributed AC systems, power grids, district heating systems, and district cooling systems. Buildings located in hot-humid regions are vulnerable to the effects of climate change. The cooling demand for Sydney might potentially grow by up to 150%, depending on the specific location and attributes of the buildings under investigation. Australia. By contrast, Tokyo's greatest significant decrease in heating demand might reach as low as -264%. Japan. In some regions, buildings use nearly 90% of their energy for cooling, and the overall energy demand for buildings is expected to increase significantly [44].

2.2. Worldwide Energy Situation

The world is in the midst of a significant global energy crisis. These extrinsic characteristics have consequences for numerous individuals, businesses, and entire economies, leading to various immediate government measures and a more extensive discussion on mitigating future disruptions. The conflicts in Russia and Ukraine were preceded by commercial pressures. However, the actions of this entity have severely disrupted the world economy by producing substantial turbulence in energy markets, undermining the progress made in recovering from the pandemic [5].

An undeniable consequence of the crisis was a surge in energy expenses. Oil prices have already exceeded USD 100 per barrel, while the natural gas prices witnessed in 2022 are unparalleled. Prices frequently exceed USD 50 per million British thermal units (MBtu) at Europe's Title Transfer Facility (TTF) hub, which is equivalent to more than USD 200 per barrel. The majority of global power generation costs, specifically 90%, may be attributed to the high expense of fuel. Furthermore, natural gas alone is responsible for over 50% of these expenditures [5,45].

As the global energy market undergoes continuous evolution and transformation, The primary objective of the global energy transition is to shift from a fossil fuel-based energy system to a low-carbon energy system, ultimately transitioning to a sustainable energy period predominantly reliant on renewable energy sources [46–48].

Consequently, renewable energy is a feasible remedy to this issue since it uses energy as efficiently as possible while reducing carbon emissions. It also helps with energy security, environmental preservation, and job creation in a number of countries. Some governments see renewable energy as the strategic pinnacle of a new era of energy technology, and they have set ambitious renewable energy objectives as part of their strategies [49–51].

2.2.1. Energy in MENA Region

The Arab region is vast and diverse, with a diversified environment known for its richness of natural resources as well as its vulnerability to climate change. It has a population of almost 400 million people, runs from the Atlantic coast of North Africa in the west to the Straits of

Hormuz in the east, and includes both affluent and impoverished republics [52].

The Arab world has the fastest-expanding energy industry, relying more on natural gas and petroleum than any other region. Regional primary energy consumption has quadrupled in the last 25 years, growing from roughly 150,000 ktoe in 1990 to around 435,000 ktoe in 2016, as shown in Fig. 8 [53].

In addition, and according to the IEA, Fig. 9 displays the electricity consumption levels of the Middle East, measured in terawatt hours (TWh), across six distinct years, spanning from 1990 to 2020. The recorded values demonstrate a consistent and notably substantial escalation in electricity demand, with consumption figures reaching 204.88 TWh in 1990 and reaching an all-time high of 1057.64 TWh in 2020 [54]. This consumption growth can be attributed to population expansion, economic development, and amplified energy requirements from various sectors, including industry, transportation, and residential establishments.

2.2.2. Egypt Strategy for Energy

Egypt, the Middle East's most populated country, confronts increased energy consumption due to fast population growth and a developing economy. This presents significant obstacles to guaranteeing a reliable and uninterrupted provision of energy and the potential for growth in the sector [55].

In line with the recommendations of the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), renewable energy has the potential to assist Egypt in satisfying its energy needs, fostering long-term economic growth, increasing employment opportunities, and contributing to the achievement of UN climate and sustainable development targets [56].

According to the International Finance Corporation (IFC), EGP 2 trillion in climate-smart investments will be needed in Egypt's energy industry by 2030. Egypt is poised to replace South Africa as Africa's largest electrical market in the coming decade [55,57].

The Ministry of Electricity and Renewable Energy's 2035 Interconnected Sustainable Energy Strategy (ISES 2035) sets out the essential requirements for promoting renewable energy development by fostering collaboration across all sectors. This affirms Egypt's grandiose objective of establishing itself as a prominent energy hub connecting Europe, Asia, and Africa. It aims to achieve this by enhancing grid interconnections within the Arab area and extending beyond. Based on Fig. 10, Egypt's objective is to increase the provision of renewable energy to 20% by 2022 and 42% by 2030 through the implementation of this strategy [58, 59].

2.3. Buildings' Energy Consumption

The substantial increase in global energy use in recent years has created a variety of concerns regarding availability, energy resource scarcity, and significant environmental consequences such as depletion of the ozone layer, global warming, and climate change. Primary energy consumption has expanded by 49% in the preceding two decades, while CO₂ emissions have increased by 43%, as reported by the Energy Information Administration (EIA) [61].

The upward trend in energy consumption will continue in the future, owing to population growth, higher demand for building services and comfort standards, an increase in time spent within buildings and HVAC systems in the building sector that consumes more energy than ever before. So, buildings' energy efficiency is increasingly becoming a top priority for regional, continental, and global energy policymakers [62].

2.3.1. Energy consumption of Egyptian Buildings

With population expansion, rising living standards, and the impacts of climate change, global buildings are consuming energy and resources at alarming rates. Recently, energy-saving techniques have been integrated into high-performance buildings, known as near-zero-Energy Buildings, a trend particularly noticeable in Egypt over the last

Fig. 8. Total final energy consumption in the Arab area by nation (ktoe) from 1990 to 2016 [53].

Fig. 9. Middle east electricity consumption [54].

decade. However, the MENA region confronts significant climate-related challenges, including a projected 50% surge in energy demand by 2040. Factors such as urbanization and strained energy infrastructures exacerbate these challenges, along with the widespread use of energy-intensive air conditioning systems in households. Additionally, inefficient cooling and refrigeration systems further strain energy resources,

while refrigerants with high global warming potential significantly contribute to emissions. Without proactive policies, emissions from cooling and refrigeration could escalate by 90% above 2017 levels by 2050 [63,64].

Buildings are one of the most energy-intensive sectors in Egypt. This sector consumes 20.1% of all the energy consumed globally. In affluent nations, building energy use represents 40% of total energy consumption [65]. The MENA region is experiencing rapid growth in this particular sector, with Egypt leading the way in terms of energy consumption in buildings among the five MENA nations [66].

Furthermore, the Ministry of Electricity’s yearly report states that buildings in Egypt utilize over 51% of energy production. The significant increase in electricity consumption in Egyptian residential buildings is mostly due to the construction of new housing developments and the widespread usage of domestic appliances, particularly air conditioners, as opposed to industrial or other purposes [67,68]. In addition, space cooling and refrigeration account for approximately 26% of total electricity usage in residential buildings. In non-residential buildings, air conditioning and other HVAC systems also use between 35 and 40 percent of the energy consumed [69].

Across more than a million square kilometers, Egypt displays a wide range of climates. The country’s diverse climatic circumstances have led

Fig. 10. Comparison between 2022 and predicted 2035 energy generation in Egypt [60].

to its categorization into eight separate regions for environmental design purposes by the Housing and Building Research Center (HBRC). Koepen's climate classification designates Egypt as having a hot desert climate (BWh) in the south and central regions and a hot steppe climate (BSh) in the coastal areas [70,71].

In Egypt, by 2050, mean annual temperature increases of two to three degrees Celsius are expected, with increased warming expected in inland areas, according to World Bank research. In addition, future projections suggest a 7% decrease in precipitation levels near coastal regions [70].

As a result, buildings' energy consumption has increased over the years due to increased HVAC system operation hours. In hot and humid climates, an increased temperature associated with high humidity levels induces discomfort. According to William et al. [72], it is desirable to minimize energy use and encourage using renewable energy resources.

2.4. Green Buildings

Green buildings, typically referred to as energy-efficient, ecologically friendly, or sustainable constructions [73], have existed since prehistoric times. Primitive humans, such as cave inhabitants, employed natural, environmentally sustainable resources and constructed their shelters to integrate with the surrounding ecosystem. Human disruption of natural equilibrium has historically resulted in considerable challenges, prompting the rise of environmental and sustainability movements. The contemporary green construction movement has gained traction in the last ten years, but its roots may be traced to the late 19th century, when the concept of sustainable practices began to emerge [74].

Green building is a popular concept all around the world. The detrimental impact of construction on the environment is a critical factor in the birth of the green building concept. This notion is the ultimate step in resolving environmental and health issues caused by buildings and limiting the consequences of the building sector on the natural environment and individuals [75,76].

Green buildings are regarded as environmentally beneficial due to their possession of these attributes. The commonly cited advantages of green buildings include energy savings of 30–40% and water conservation of 20–30%, enhanced indoor air quality, better health and productivity, increased value of the property, and improved natural lighting and ventilation, among numerous other advantages [77,78]. While the environmental advantages of eco-friendly buildings are obvious, there are additional compelling reasons for undertaking green building projects that may not be immediately apparent. Below are a few illustrations: (i) Enhanced employee satisfaction and improved health in green buildings, demonstrated by advancements in respiratory and allergy conditions, as well as reduced incidence of migraines. (ii) decreased energy expenses. (iii) Increased ability to attract and retain high-quality employees. (iv) Potential for higher resale value compared to conventional buildings. (v) Expanded business opportunities that cater to the growing conscientious consumer market [79].

2.4.1. Egypt's Green Buildings Potential

Egypt, similar to numerous countries globally, is facing continuous pressure due to increasing rates of urbanization. Main Egyptian cities lack green spaces due to dense urban development and confined roadways [80,81]. In this context, several global building assessment rating tools have been developed in recent years to measure buildings' sustainability performance. To promote sustainable building and compare green building performance, many countries have developed Green Building Rating Systems (GBRSs). Some countries have adapted foreign GBRSs, while others have created new ones [82].

The Egyptian Green Building Council (GBC-Egypt) was formed in 2009 in Egypt with the goal of advocating for green construction practices. The Green Pyramid Rating System (GPRS) was first introduced in April 2011, with a second version released in 2017 that expanded on the

principles of the LEED system. The GPRS, created by the Housing and Building National Centre (HBRC), is tailored to Egypt's Vision 2030 and customized to fit the country's distinct circumstances [83]. Achieving a certain percentage of points in different sustainability criteria determines the recognition level. However, studies have identified challenges to effectively implementing GPRS. Some buildings have been certified, while others, although fulfilling sustainable criteria, have not obtained enough points for certification [84].

Additionally, it has come to attention that the national Egyptian building code does not explicitly mention the rating system and that some of the GPRS criteria do not fully adhere to it [85]. Recommendations have been suggested to improve the rating criteria to more closely match national priorities, such as socioeconomic and environmental concerns. It highlights the necessity of aligning the GPRS with local building regulations to guarantee consistency and backing for green building projects in Egypt. Proposals have been put forward to enhance the national building code by incorporating international standards for high-performance green buildings. This aims to create a smooth connection between regulatory frameworks and sustainability rating systems [86,87].

In the pursuit of effectively addressing the prevailing challenges confronting Egypt, the Worldwide Green Council has proffered a salient recommendation. It advocates for the proactive engagement of the Egyptian government in fostering the implementation of 'green' buildings. This initiative underscores a concerted effort toward promoting sustainable architectural practices as a pivotal strategy for mitigating environmental concerns and advancing socio-economic development in the region [22].

Furthermore, the EPBD recommendations emphasize the significance of NZEB as a vital feature in contemporary sustainable building practices. NZEBs, known for their superior energy efficiency, support the suggested approach by utilizing renewable energy sources for on-site power production. This highlights a unified strategy for sustainable growth in the constructed environment, as advocated by the council's suggestion [23].

2.5. Nearly Zero Buildings Definition

NZEB, according to Iqbal et al., is a building that integrates commercially available renewable energy technology with energy-efficient building strategies to eliminate the use of fossil fuels [88].

Kilkis described NZEB as a building with a total annual quantity of zero energy transfer throughout all-electric and other transfers that occurred within a specific period [89].

The literature on zero energy is gaining popularity as a result of the definition of NZEBs. The majority of study papers mostly concentrate on showcasing different zero-Energy Buildings. However, there is a diverse collection of extensively documented publications. It facilitated the investigation of the interpretation and definition of the concept of net zero Energy Building. Fig. 11 illustrates the fundamental principles of Net Zero Energy Building, where the total energy demand of the building is met entirely by renewable energy sources generated on-site. If that is inadequate, electricity from the nearby electrical grid can be

Fig. 11. NZEB's idea [90].

utilized. If the energy produced by the renewable energy sources on the premises is greater than what the building needs, the surplus energy can be supplied to the local power grid [90–93].

2.6. Nearly Zero Energy Buildings

Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) are solid solutions for providing sustainable and energy-efficient buildings that produce energy. The development strategy provides us with the resources we need to study the relationship between today's environmental concerns and the probability of their progression in the future [94]. Concerns regarding the relevance of energy management initiatives have arisen due to a greater understanding of global population expansion and the significant environmental effects of current resource degradation practices. The building sector is becoming more interested in establishing tight energy-saving targets [95].

The world market for products and services associated with NZEB building and renovation is predicted to increase at a cumulative annual growth rate of 44.5% between 2014 and 2035, topping \$1.4 trillion last years. This is how the NZEB concept is gaining traction [90]. Fig. 12 presents NZEB revenue projections for products and services over the next two decades. These projections are compiled from a variety of sources, including industry reports, market research studies, with Navigant Research's NZEB report serving as the primary source [96].

2.6.1. NZEB Achievement

D'Agostino and Parker proposed a paradigm for cost-optimal NZEB design. This framework analysis incorporates cost, energy price, and climatic data. One remarkable result is that the most frequent optimum NZEB configuration includes better insulation, building airtightness, class A++ devices, lights, home-based energy management systems, and PV. Depending on the environment, airtightness and insulation (colder climates) or appliance efficiency and minimizing solar gains (warmer climates) must come first [97].

2.7. Building Energy Management and Conservation

Within the following 20 years, building energy consumption is predicted to climb by more than 40%. Electricity is the most often used energy source in buildings, and demand is rising. Initiatives to boost building energy efficiency are essential to counterbalance the impact of increased demand. Residential buildings will see an increase in energy consumption due to home appliances, water, and space heating. In contrast, non-residential structures will increase energy consumption due to space heating and other miscellaneous equipment [98].

2.7.1. Building Performance Simulation

Building performance simulation (BPS), also referred to as 'building simulation' or 'building energy modeling and simulation,' involves the utilization of software to assess the energy efficiency of a building. BPS can be utilized to assess environmental performance, namely in terms of daylighting and thermal efficiency. Furthermore, the utilization of building simulation can greatly decrease the overall expenditures during the lifespan of a building. In particular, building thermal modeling proves to be highly valuable in assessing energy-conserving methods in buildings. Multiple design alternatives can be analyzed to identify the most efficient solution with the least expensive overall cost that meets all the design requirements set by the architects and engineers [99,100].

Implementing energy-saving strategies, assessing energy consumption, and monitoring energy in buildings is referred to as energy management. Global process optimization necessitates comprehensive control of all building flows and factors. Several researchers have explored this topic in this area.

Gardel [101], Irulegia [102], Maheshwari [103], and El-Gendy [104] researched changing university buildings into NZEBs using simulation tools, where Gardel was able to reduce the energy consumption of a university building located on Reunion Island to one-third of a typical building with a 2% cost increase [101]. While Irulegia surveyed in order to increase the energy efficiency of an educational university building in Spain toward reaching the NZEB goal, as educational buildings account for 20% of non-residential floor space there, a survey was done among students of the Faculty of Architecture in San Sebastian to know their comfort zone concerning temperature. It was found that most of the students prefer temperatures lower than stated by the theoretical comfort model. With the aid of the simulation tool LIDER, 58% of the energy savings in the whole building after retrofitting actions were done [102]. According to Maheshwari, a case study on the Moradabad Institute of Technology campus was undertaken in an attempt to convert it to a NZEB by producing its energy demands using renewable energy resources. Following studies, photovoltaic solar panels were determined to be the best alternative for generating power and were put on the building's backside to absorb the most direct sunlight [103]. Moreover, to keep up with development, a study on historical buildings was made to increase the energy efficiency of these buildings and reduce CO₂ emissions produced. The study was done in a room inside the faculty of the engineering building, using simulation software (Diva-for-Rhino and Autodesk Vasari) to improve and evaluate the energy performance of the building. A 39.2% decrease in energy consumption was achieved after some improvements were made, such as the height of the window, type of glazing, and shading devices, as reported by El-Gendy [104].

Mekkawi [105], Krarti [106], and Albadrya [107] conducted a study on the feasibility of transforming and developing residential buildings

Fig. 12. NZEB revenue by products and services for the next two decades [90,96].

toward achieving NZEB. Through using energy simulation tools (DesignBuilder, Diva-for-Rhino), a study was made on a two-story housing prototype in Alexandria to know the actual impact of design parameters that highly affect the building performance concerning cooling and heating loads and help to improve the design during the early design stage to reach the net-zero energy goal with the aid of building integrated photovoltaic units and changing design parameters and decisions according to their eligibility for different challenges in the climatic region. Alexandria, a 38.2% reduction in total energy consumption can be achieved, as reported by Mekki [105]. Krarti conducted a study on the effect of net-zero energy residential buildings in the Mena region on energy usage, using a new design to substitute the existing residential building with the aid of modeling and optimization techniques for over 160 MENA locations, taking into account several variables that have a direct impact on energy consumption, such as orientation, window dimension and location, glazed window type, wall and roof insulation levels, and illumination fix. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that PV systems of 2.5–3.0 kW are required for attaining net-zero energy home designs in the majority of MENA area locations [106]. In addition, Albadya carried out a case study on an existing residential building in Cairo to convert it to NZEB. It has been found that existing buildings have high energy consumption due to a lack of insulation, which makes it challenging to reach thermal comfort for occupants. Using a simulation program (by selecting available insulation and integrating PV panels to produce energy), it was found that it is possible to reach NZEB, and it is economically affordable [107].

Mynhardt [108] assessed the yearly energy performance of a recently constructed teaching institution in Southern Africa using the Southern African Green Star grading scale and national energy-efficiency construction rules. A quantitative physical modeling technique was utilized to evaluate the building's energy performance, utilizing EnergyPlus as the energy and thermal load simulation engine. The analysis discovered that the physical building utilizes 16.5% more energy per year than the hypothetical building. A Green Star rating was declared unreachable based on data collected during the initial design stage since the GSSA energy conditional requirements were not satisfied. The investigation found the HVAC system and lights as the key contributors to the large variance in energy usage. Despite having a 62.9% greater lighting power density, the HVAC system in the hypothetical building was found to be more efficient than the FCUs system employed in the actual structure. To estimate potential energy savings, the author analyzed the actual building fabric and the HVAC and lighting systems. Lastly, the author discovered that by decreasing the intensity of lighting and implementing a more effective HVAC system, it is possible to significantly decrease the building's total energy consumption, leading to a reduced ecological impact. The study also encompassed a concise economic evaluation of these energy-conserving possibilities, illustrating that the required capital expenditure would be justifiable.

Attia et al. [109] conducted research to develop simulated energy sets of data and baseline models for Egypt's residential sector. They conducted an in-depth study of Egyptian residential units and analyzed the data using two building simulation models, Energy Plus. According to the findings, simulation models must be evaluated against apartment attributes. Consequently, the researchers developed two building performance simulation models that replicated the average energy consumption characteristics of air conditioning in Alexandria, Cairo, and Asyut, Egypt. These simulation models were used to examine the energy usage profiles for lights, air conditioning systems, domestic hot water, and appliances. The study's primary goal was to assess the energy and economic consequences of Egypt's new energy standard in the future. As a result, the researchers created two complete models that may be utilized for this purpose.

2.7.2. Building Envelope

Enhancing the building envelope, which is comprised of the walls, roof, and windows and acts as a barrier separating the inside and outside

of the building, would reduce the amount of heat transmitted to the inside [107].

It is generally recognized that building envelopes significantly influence building thermal performance; consequently, moisture and heat transfer management should be included in hot-climatic locations [110]. Furthermore, the building envelope influences both energy usage and maximum loads. Consumption of energy and peak electrical demands increase when the insulation efficiency of the building envelope decreases. This thermal layer should offer adequate heat flow resistance across the building structure, which may be accomplished by selecting the proper insulation [111], materials that undergo phase transition [112] or adapted facades [113]. Thermal insulation may greatly reduce building cooling demands in hot areas. [114], facades with two skins [115], or energy-saving approaches are used [116]. The most common method, however, is applying insulating material coatings to non-transparent exterior walls. Envelope quality can be enhanced by making incremental adjustments to the designs of walls, roofs, or windows using simulation models and building load calculations [117]. Various methodologies are currently being devised to create energy models that accurately simulate a building or plant model in order to forecast energy consumption or financial advantages [118].

Utilizing effective building and renovation techniques is crucial. The revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) has prompted EU member states to enact stricter regulations on thermal insulation in buildings in order to mitigate the environmental impact of the construction sector. Thermal insulation is a highly successful approach to reducing a building's energy consumption for heating while simultaneously improving indoor thermal comfort. The optimal thickness of insulation increases as the number of heating days rises. However, the impact of this on the cooling phase is a subject of debate, and whether it improves or exacerbates the overheating phenomenon is contingent on various factors [119,120]. Remarkably, numerous building shapes with varying thermal transmission enclosures were investigated in a variety of European climates. The findings suggest that in southern regions, it is necessary to have a shell with a higher thermal transmittance in order to mitigate issues related to overheated environments [121,122].

Researchers have found that while highly insulated lightweight building envelopes increase the risk of overheating, having an interior mass and implementing proper ventilation can mitigate this risk. However, previous studies have mainly focused on moderate and temperate climates. In hot-arid climates, the opposite occurs, where high thermal resistance envelopes increase the risk of overheating due to the persistent heat flow from the high daily temperatures. The thick insulation layer effectively prevents this heat from penetrating the structure, thus creating a potential overheating threat that needs to be addressed [123–125]. Nonetheless, the effects of insulation on a building must be evaluated on an annualized basis, considering both cooling and heating demands, because, in mild regions, higher heating performance exceeds cooling drawbacks [126].

To outline, thermal insulation is essential for improving energy efficiency. Thermal insulation reduces energy usage and, hence, has a lower environmental effect. As a result, proper insulation of the whole building is crucial to reducing heat gain and loss via the building envelope. The thickness of the insulating material must be optimized in light of the energy savings realized throughout the whole life cycle of the structure in contrast to its total cost [127,128].

When it comes to building design and energy management, multiple factors need to be considered. These include the type and purpose of the building, its size and orientation, the thermal properties of materials used, prevailing weather conditions, and the type and efficiency of the air conditioning system in place. Other important considerations include electricity pricing and usage patterns. [129,130]. Researchers and academics worldwide have conducted several studies within that approach.

According to Al-Homoud [131], buildings consume a considerable quantity of energy in all countries, particularly in locations with severe weather, where a substantial supply of energy is required to heat and

cool buildings effectively. Several measures may be employed to reduce the demand for heating and cooling. However, the most important is proper design and material selection for the building envelope. Thermal insulation used properly in buildings may significantly decrease the capacity of the air-conditioning system and the associated energy expenses. It can also extend the duration of thermal comfort without using mechanical air conditioning during the off-season. Thermal insulation in various building types and insulating materials can help minimize cooling and heating costs.

Bolatturk [132] suggests that using insulating materials is among the most effective methods to conserve energy in buildings. He recommends that engineering studies be conducted to determine the appropriate insulation thickness for each building. The prevailing weather conditions influence the design of the building walls. For instance, in warm areas, bricks or concrete bricks are covered with thin layers of plaster; in cold climates, sandwich walls are employed. Bolatturk employed extruded polystyrene board as an insulating element in his investigation and determined that the ideal thickness for building insulation utilizing polystyrene boards is between 3.2 and 3.8 cm.

Based on Pargana et al. [133], insulation installation is a theoretically feasible method for reducing building energy consumption. This study examined the environmental consequences and energy usage linked to different conventional thermal insulation materials. The research findings suggest that using insulating materials is a promising approach to decrease energy consumption and foster the growth of sustainable buildings in the Portuguese context.

Aditya et al. [134] propose that thermal insulation, with its environmentally sustainable features, is a viable technique for addressing energy consumption in buildings while maintaining optimal thermal comfort. As the thickness of the insulating material increases, the thermal conductivity decreases. However, the insulation cost increases proportionately and will eventually surpass the potential savings, resulting in no financial advantage to increased thickness. Therefore, an optimal insulation thickness exists at which further increases do not lead to significant cost savings. The study highlights the importance of building insulation as a means of resource conservation and reducing greenhouse gas emissions associated with building energy consumption.

In their research, Evin and Ucar [135] studied the effectiveness of thermal insulation in four different residential building envelopes in Turkey's diverse climatic zones. The researchers tested four types of insulation materials. Their findings indicate that energy costs are significantly reduced when XPS is used to insulate the roof compared to uninsulated roofs. The authors recommend applying this method to other building types and weather conditions.

According to El-Sherif et al. [136], the researchers investigated the current state of an exemplary existing administrative building in Cairo, Egypt. The study examines the economic viability of transforming a leading-edge current administrative building into a virtual and net-zero Energy Building. The addition of three layers of insulation resulted in a decrease in the U-value from 0.28 W/m² to 0.2, 0.19, and 0.18 W/m², respectively. The U-value with the lowest value resulted in the lowest energy consumption (279.396 kWh/m². a) compared to the baseline usage (279.955 kWh/m². a).

Moreover, the heat that comes in through the glazing, such as windows, glass curtain walls, and skylights, is the most considerable cooling load. The glazing style will almost certainly be double low-e glazing if the building is built to meet the energy targets of ASHRAE Model 90.1 2010 or later. Most HVAC designers expect single glazing as a safety factor, contributing to higher cooling loads [137]. Several research studies in this field have investigated this area.

Dutta et al. [138] To minimize the cooling load of buildings in tropical climates, several glazing options were investigated. Several simulation models are used to investigate five distinct types of single and double-glazing, each with a unique potential for energy savings. TRNSYS and eQuest modeling tools were utilized to simulate five varieties of commonly available window glasses, which were then validated

using lab-tested findings. According to studies, the solar heat gain coefficient (SHGC) is a more critical factor in glazing than the U-value in the context of reducing building energy cooling loads.

According to Fathalian et al. [139], it is not easy to make an educated decision about the impact of various energy-saving strategies without using energy modeling tools. The authors of this study used Design-Builder software to determine the annual energy consumption of an Iranian office building. They validated the simulation results using the building's monthly energy use, which was 1.6% off. The authors proposed three methods for reducing energy use, beginning with replacing single-glazed windows with double Low-E glazing windows. Researchers next looked into adding a thermal insulation layer to the structure's outer wall, utilizing horizontal shadings on the outside, and removing the inner shades. According to the findings, these strategies lowered energy consumption by 14%, 18%, and 13%, respectively.

In research done by Ghose et al. [140] on refurbished buildings in New Zealand, the authors offer alternative measures to reduce their environmental implications. To reduce energy usage in larger institutions, the study recommends prioritizing the installation of efficient HVAC systems and lowering the window-wall ratio. Materials with lower environmental implications, on the other hand, should be considered for compact buildings. Furthermore, the research emphasizes the significance of substantial energy retrofitting measures for all refurbished buildings, resulting in a minimum 60% decrease in operational energy usage. These findings indicate the need to evaluate various measures to lessen the environmental impact of buildings.

Expanding upon prior research concerning the influence of building envelopes on energy efficiency and indoor comfort, Table 1 broadens the analysis to include a wider array of sophisticated building envelope technologies. This encompasses the incorporation of phase-change materials, thermal insulation layers, and advanced roofing solutions, including green roofs, reflective coatings, and solar-enhanced designs. The table consolidates findings from recent research, including quantitative comparisons of energy savings, enhancements to indoor environments, and lifespan cost-effectiveness.

2.8. Lighting

Lighting systems consume a significant amount of energy, particularly in buildings. Thus, creating energy-efficient systems would significantly contribute to building energy savings [145], since lighting significantly impacts energy usage owing to various factors. One of these is that illumination has an impact on other energy-consuming sources. As a result, lighting performance affects such sources, which appropriate research investigations must address. According to a research study published, a correct calculation of energy consumed by lighting in a building must consider the interaction of lighting with other consumers, such as heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC). Efficient lighting control results in higher energy savings rates for many buildings and systems [146].

Numerous solutions are often employed in lighting system (LSs) designs in buildings to achieve a significant degree of energy savings. Several peer-reviewed articles have proposed three main energy-saving tactics employed by LSs in the literature. LSs based on occupancy profiles, schedules, and daylight fluctuations are commonly used by energy management systems to attain building energy efficiency [147–149]. Many academics have looked into and investigated the extent to which the lighting load is related to the other loads in the building.

Ahn et al. [150] conducted a study on the impact of lighting on cooling and heating demands and found that LED lighting has the potential to save energy. Additionally, it was observed that multiple countries have enacted laws to promote the adoption of this technology due to its superior efficiency and longer durability compared to traditional lighting systems. The EnergyPlus simulation tool was utilized to assess the energy usage of many light fixtures in Daejeon, Korea, as well as a virtual building provided through the United States Department of

Table 1
Synthesis of building envelope technologies with energy and cost insights.

Authors	Methodology	Key Findings	Contribution
William et al [21].	The use of reflective paints as part of a retrofitting strategy to improve energy efficiency in three Egyptian cities: Aswan, Cairo, and Alexandria	Aswan, Cairo, and Alexandria correspondingly save 21%, 19%, and 17% of their energy. Notable gains in energy economy and thermal comfort.	Emphasized how reflecting paints may save energy in various regions and provided workable ideas for hot-climate energy-efficient buildings.
Ibrahim et al [141].	A comparative investigation of radiative coatings, thermal insulation, and GIPV in hot and humid regions	Radiative coatings provide a 13.1% energy savings. The integration of GIPV results in an energy savings of 34.9%. Cost-effective, with an LCOS of \$0.045/kWh for radiative coatings and \$0.052/kWh for insulation and coatings combined.	Demonstrated the usefulness of envelope-enhancing strategies in lowering energy consumption and carbon emissions, pointing to GIPV as a major solution for nearly-zero Energy Buildings.
Buonomano et al [142].	Providing a dynamic simulation model for NZEBs to analyze PCM, BIPV/BIPV-T, and daylight control	Energy savings: 16.9% (13.3% without PCM). Optimized building configurations for NZEBs, resulting in net zero energy performance.	An new simulation model for measuring NZEBs was presented, providing valuable insights into energy-saving techniques such as PCM and BIPV/BIPV-T for Mediterranean climates.
Asghari et al [143].	Simulations of external wall construction using PCM, TILs, and combination techniques in residential buildings.	37.88% reductions in thermal energy and 26.75% savings in cooling achieved by the combination of PCM and TIL.	Revealed the synergistic impact of PCM and TILs on thermal efficiency, offering a cost-effective approach to diminish energy use in buildings.
Abu Qadourah [144]	Parametric study used simulations to assess the impact of green roofs on energy consumption, indoor temperature, and carbon emissions reduction.	Green roofs decreased annual energy usage by as much as 12%. Variable soil depths affected energy use, indoor temperature, and carbon mitigation.	Emphasizes the efficacy of green roofs as a sustainable passive approach to improving energy performance in Mediterranean climates, particularly in office buildings in Amman.
Ibrahim et al [36].	Thorough evaluation of diverse roof improvement methods (green roofs, solar gardens, reflecting paint coatings, and thermal insulation) at four locations, emphasizing energy conservation and cost analysis.	Green roofs and solar technology collectively lowered energy consumption by 40%. The application of reflective paint resulted in a 12.96% decrease. Thermal insulation exhibited the minimal savings at 2.65%. Reflective paint was the most economical option, costing between \$0.12 and \$0.17 per kilowatt-hour. Green roofs and solar gardens demonstrated	Highlights the significance of region-specific solutions to enhance energy efficiency, providing customized advice for urban planners and policymakers to cultivate energy-efficient, sustainable communities.

Table 1 (continued)

Authors	Methodology	Key Findings	Contribution
			economic viability, yielding savings ranging from \$3.53 to \$2.16 per kilowatt-hour.

Energy. LED lighting is better suited for regulating mechanisms compared to normal fluorescent lighting. Moreover, implementing LED lights in conjunction with this management strategy for the purpose of cooling could potentially enhance energy efficiency.

Miyaoka et al. [151] investigated the influence of LED lighting on the air conditioning and energy consumption of commercial buildings. The authors assert that the air conditioning demand resulting from illumination is directly correlated with the lamp's electricity consumption. Therefore, substituting conventional fluorescents with LEDs will decrease the energy consumption required for air conditioning. The researchers evaluated the air-conditioning requirements and usage at a retail establishment specializing in electronics in central Japan over a one-year period. This was accomplished by analyzing the thermal properties of fluorescent and LED lighting. By substituting fluorescent bulbs with LEDs, they reduced the annual cooling load by 17%. As a result, the annual electricity usage for lights and air conditioning decreased by 21%.

2.9. Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning systems

HVAC systems' energy consumption is regarded as essential since it depends on them to achieve adequate thermal comfort. In both residential and non-residential markets, this is the major energy usage [62]. Many sources demonstrate that significant increases in air conditioning consumption generate substantial supply problems, particularly for developing nations, during peak loading periods [66].

Hoyt et al. [152] conducted a simulation study to investigate the impact of changing heating and cooling set points on energy consumption in medium-sized office buildings across seven ASHRAE climatic zones [153]. The study included six unique office buildings, representing either a building control retrofit or a newly constructed building. The authors found that increasing the cooling set point from 22.2 to 25°C resulted in a 29% reduction in cooling energy and a 27% reduction in overall HVAC usage without compromising occupant comfort. The study also found that using additional temperature bands provided by fans or human controls can result in HVAC energy savings ranging from 32% to 73%, depending on the environment. Additionally, lowering the VAV (variable air volume) minimum flow fractions was found to have a significant impact on HVAC energy consumption, resulting in an average savings of 31%. The authors also noted that energy savings through cooling and fans ranged from 15% to 38%. These findings provide valuable insights into potential energy-saving measures that can be implemented in office buildings through adjustments to heating and cooling set points and building control systems.

Elharidi et al. [154] discovered that employing natural ventilation and individually controlled localized cooling systems in Egyptian offices consumes less than half the energy required by centrally serviced buildings. The authors also mentioned that changing tenant behavior and implementing energy-efficient systems such as HVAC, lighting, and appliances can result in a 30% reduction in energy use. Furthermore, they proposed that government actions to promote energy-efficient technology and energy-conscious behavior may result in a 50% reduction in conventional office energy use. Overall, the study underlines the relevance of tenant behavior and the use of energy-efficient technologies in lowering energy consumption in office buildings.

According to Emil and Diab [63], buildings consume 66–74% of Egypt's energy. They used EnergyPlus to evaluate the impact of

implementing energy-saving measures on a Cairo educational facility in order to reach the optimal energy need. It was discovered that retrofitting the walls, roof, and windows saved about 29% of the energy. Additionally, upgrading the HVAC mechanical systems resulted in yearly energy savings of more than 50%.

2.9.1. Air Conditioning Systems Right Sizing

For maximum energy efficiency and comfort, hot climates like Egypt require cooling systems to have an appropriate capacity, according to the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) in the United States. Large-scale equipment incurs greater upfront expenses, exhibits diminished efficiency, necessitates increased energy consumption, and has the potential to cause discomfort. Therefore, it is crucial to choose the appropriate equipment size, particularly in humid conditions where rapid cycling of air conditioning systems can lead to inadequate humidity control. In addition, larger systems require increased fan power for the blower in order to accommodate higher working duct pressures. Researchers have taken into account multiple aspects when calculating the heating and cooling loads, such as the building envelope (which includes walls, roof, windows, floor space, insulation value, and thickness), building orientation, roof surface color, and occupancy [155]. Several researchers have researched this issue.

According to Djunaedy et al. [156], design engineers often opt for large HVAC systems to provide a margin of safety and account for potential periods of increased demand beyond the originally specified limits. This results in increased equipment costs and ongoing expenses related to maintenance and energy consumption. Unfortunately, consumers are often not fully informed about the challenges associated with these heightened safety considerations. A cost-benefit analysis is recommended to determine the economic benefits of such an approach.

Using data from long-term field observations, Woradechjurnroen et al. [157] evaluate the consequences of oversizing HVAC systems in commercial buildings. Retail outlets are used as a sample example of typical commercial buildings to investigate the condition of equipment oversizing and its impact on energy usage. The study can compute the average energy charge associated with sample buildings and evaluate the degree of oversizing. Engineers can also use the data as a standard to evaluate building load design.

2.9.2. Outdoor Design conditions

Outdoor design conditions are meteorological data that describe the climate features of a certain area and are utilized for design reasons. Climate information such as air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation may be supplied. The design terminology of heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems and energy efficiency depends on [158].

In the HVAC design phase, the standard strategy is to compute peak load capacity at a certain hour of the design day, utilizing interior and outdoor design parameters. Outdoor design conditions are used to generate design weather data, which depicts the severe and predominant environmental conditions under which the building will function [159]. These are used in design load calculations to determine peak design loads, HVAC equipment capacity, and plant capacity. Following the assessment of equipment sizes and system configurations, year-round energy calculations utilizing typical meteorological data may be utilized to determine yearly and seasonal energy demands [160].

Design conditions have a direct impact on the load on HVAC equipment. Different sets of external design circumstances can impact equipment and plant sizes, building operating strategies and reactions, inside thermal comfort, and building energy use. If the optimal design for beginning costs and building energy efficiency is to be achieved, the design criteria must be carefully specified [161].

Indeed, as global temperatures continue to rise, the frequency and intensity of extreme high-temperature events are increasing, even in traditionally temperate regions. This trend is expected to continue and result in a severe escalation of such events, including their frequency,

intensity, and duration. This poses significant health risks for residents, including an increased likelihood of death due to high indoor temperatures and reduced cognitive function and productivity. Moreover, high indoor temperatures can exacerbate respiratory and cardiovascular conditions, particularly in vulnerable populations. These impacts are particularly concerning in schools and workplaces, where people spend a significant amount of time indoors [162,163].

2.9.3. Indoor Air Quality

The NZEB objective is set for both new and heavily renovated buildings. In light of the low energy performance of the current building stock, this is the most challenging obstacle to meeting energy and environmental requirements [164].

Even though much NZEB research focuses on energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness [165], seeking sufficient IEQ levels influences building energy demand. Building designers confront a complex problem in providing IEQ at the lowest possible energy cost since poor air quality and thermal comfort make people more susceptible to illness [166–169].

The following are the primary reasons for low IEQ levels: HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) system design issues [170, 171], excessive thermal insulation in the building envelope, and ineffective design and implementation of passive technologies and methods [172–174].

2.10. Energy Generation and Storage

Global implementation of innovations in technology, politics, and markets is currently taking place on a worldwide scale (IRENA, 2019a). Considerable advancements have been achieved in the domains of electric mobility, battery storage, digital technologies, and artificial intelligence, among various other areas. These trends are also garnering increased attention towards the imperative of sustainable mining and management of rare earths and other minerals, as well as the necessity of investing in the circular economy. Emerging intelligent grid systems, spanning from small-scale to large-scale grids, are being supported by enabling laws and markets, thereby improving the power industry's capacity to manage the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources. Renewable energy sources, such as bioenergy and green hydrogen, are being actively employed to address the pressing challenges in the domains of transportation, construction, and industrial sectors [53].

The utilization of renewable power sources has the potential to mitigate the reliance on fossil fuel energy consumption through the implementation of Net Zero Energy Building principles and categorizations. One potential approach involves the exportation of surplus photovoltaic (PV) or wind energy to the grid, which can effectively mitigate natural gas consumption. [175]. As delineated in the European Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) reprint, the subsequent characteristics are attributed to Net Zero Energy Buildings: The objective should be to significantly reduce energy demand and rely predominantly on renewable resources to fulfill energy requirements [176]. In order to attain Net Zero Energy, it is important to incorporate photovoltaic (PV) systems that can provide a minimum of 30% of the total energy requirements [177]. The utilization of solar panels should not be limited solely to meeting a building's electricity requirements in order to attain the net zero energy objective. There exists an additional significance in the shading effect produced by solar panels, which serves to mitigate surface temperature and subsequently reduce the overall energy consumption of the building [178].

The increasing curiosity about on-site energy production has prompted the emergence of various research papers on the topic of PV [179]. Several studies have investigated the optimization of PV systems by analyzing aspects including panel orientation, quantity of panels, inclination, and direction. A proposed framework seeks to maximize energy production in various climate zones by considering horizontal irradiation levels. Research has also explored ways to reduce the mismatch between electricity produced and loads, therefore improving

the efficiency of photovoltaic systems. These efforts together help improve the comprehension and application of optimal PV systems in different environmental circumstances [180,181].

On top of that, depending on when it occurs, the mismatch can be segmented into components that occur daily, weekly, and seasonal. The diurnal pattern is most noticeable in the hourly discrepancy, with solar power generation surpassing electricity demand during the day and no generation occurring at night. Weekly inconsistencies frequently occur due to 24-hour power shortages resulting from extended extreme weather conditions, like persistently dark or windless days, causing limited solar or wind power production. Seasonal fluctuations also have a role in causing discrepancies, especially throughout specific months [180,182–184].

Regrettably, wind patterns are not consistently present, and solar radiation is not perpetually available. In order to address the demand for power during periods of unavailability of solar and wind energy, it is imperative to store the excess energy generated by these renewable sources rather than curtail it. Fuel cells (FCs) and lithium-ion batteries, together with other technological advancements, are currently emerging as feasible storage solutions. Batteries are commonly regarded as a cost-effective and efficient alternative to stationary hydrogen fuel cells, often demonstrating superior round-trip efficiency. In contrast, hydrogen storage systems and fuel cells (FCs) exhibit the advantageous characteristics of little self-discharge, extended operational lifespans, and enhanced tolerance to elevated temperatures. These attributes render them particularly valuable in geographically challenging areas, such as the Middle East [185].

In continuation of this line of thinking, Mohammadi and Bahman (2024) provide a "5Z concept" for energy-autonomous buildings (ABs) in warm regions, with an emphasis on achieving complete independence from the grid, eliminating energy costs, carbon emissions, and any grid connections. Their research emphasizes the amalgamation of renewable energy and energy storage systems, illustrating that a 50% reduction in energy demand decreases battery capacity requirements from 3415 kWh to 1710 kWh and solar panels from 362 to 181. This methodology enhances energy systems, minimizes expenses, and promotes sustainable urban infrastructure and transportation solutions [186].

In summary, energy storage technology emphasizes the sporadic nature of renewable sources like wind and solar, leading to an excess or inadequate production of energy. Therefore, energy storage systems are crucial in dealing with this fluctuation. Recent research on energy storage systems provides a thorough analysis of several energy storage systems, outlining their development, operational principles, and characteristics. Every system has distinct benefits and constraints that are customized to meet specific performance criteria. Pumped-hydro and thermal storage systems are commonly used for large-scale applications, whereas battery energy storage systems are specifically suggested for high power and energy requirements. Moreover, super capacitors, superconducting magnetic energy storage, and flywheel energy storage are well-suited for situations that require shorter durations and quick responses. Although there are concerns regarding efficiency and cost, hydrogen and methane storage show possibilities for future scalability because of their promising storage capacities. Despite their high cost, chemical energy storage devices continue to be widely used, and current research efforts are mostly directed towards waste management and recycling. Given the changing energy demands and environmental regulations, it is crucial to develop innovative energy storage technologies [187].

3. Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Buildings

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to a collection of computerized systems that are capable of carrying out tasks that are comparable to those performed by humans, achieving a level of perception, reasoning, interaction, and learning that is similar to that of humans. AI systems possess the ability to modify their behavior without requiring explicit re-

programming, thereby showcasing their intelligence through the process of learning from their surroundings and applying acquired information to novel scenarios. This mechanism differentiates sentient beings from non-sentient machines, illustrating the manifestation of intellect [188,189].

The increasing worries over global warming and climate change have emphasized the necessity of sustainable energy practices, in which residential and commercial buildings have a crucial impact on total energy usage. In response to this, the notion of net-zero Energy Buildings has become increasingly important, with the goal of achieving an equilibrium between annual power generation and consumption. Nevertheless, there are ongoing difficulties arising from discrepancies between the demand and supply of energy, which are produced by consumer behavior and weather conditions. As a result, it is imperative to employ sophisticated solutions for the purpose of optimizing energy management. This literature review highlights a significant contribution in the form of an effective hybrid AI-based framework that has been proposed for accurate prediction of power use and generation. The framework comprises efficient data pre-processing, extraction of spatiotemporal features using ConvLSTM and BDGRU, and forecasting utilizing multilayer perceptron layers. The model's strong performance is confirmed through comprehensive tests, which include ablation studies. These experiments demonstrate a significant decrease in errors compared to the most advanced techniques currently available. The suggested model, designed specifically for short-term single-step forecasting at an hourly resolution, showcases its suitability for real-time energy prediction in local power networks. The study admits its constraints in making long-term predictions. The document provides a well-defined plan for future tasks, highlighting the creation of a versatile model that can make predictions in the short, medium, and long term. It also takes into account the size of the model and the ability to execute it in real-time on edge devices. This study adds to the expanding corpus of knowledge on sustainable energy practices and establishes a basis for future progress in predictive modeling for energy consumption and generation [190].

AI in green buildings (GBs) is categorized into four prominent fields of research. One of the primary uses of AI-in-GB is in the field of knowledge discovery and the creation of fuzzy rules. The development of fuzzy logic stemmed from the aspiration to educate computer systems using human knowledge [191]. The application of Zadeh's [192] fuzzy set theory (FST) has been used to address multi-criteria objectives and GB uncertainties in fuzzy decision environments.

Another utilization is big data, which refers to data sets that are characterized by their great volume and rapid velocity, which standard databases are unable to effectively gather, manage, and process due to their large variety and size. Big data analytics can effectively analyze structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data utilizing advanced artificial intelligence techniques. Data mining is a computational method that is utilized to uncover concealed knowledge from extensive datasets and convert this knowledge into a comprehensible framework for subsequent decision-making. GBs are currently equipped with sensors, including temperature sensors, power meters, and flow meters. These sensors are capable of generating large amounts of data in real-time, thanks to the progress made in smart metering and building automation technology. Regularly gathered building data can be analyzed to aid facility managers in enhancing operational efficiency and minimizing energy waste [193–195].

Furthermore, the utilization of AI in GB involves the implementation of intelligent optimization and building automation technologies. Intelligent optimization refers to the use of AI approaches to uncover Pareto optimal solutions. This process mostly utilizes multi-objective optimization algorithms like Genetic Algorithms (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [196,197]. Building automation systems, often known as smart-GB, employ data from the actual activities of a building to provide real-time monitoring and control. These technologies enhance facility management by detecting anomalies in energy

usage patterns and incorporating additional parameters such as building materials and weather conditions. AI techniques, such as fuzzy logic and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) classification, are essential in building automation for automatic building diagnostics, fault identification, and diagnostics. These methods enhance the efficiency and sustainability of Green Buildings [193,198].

After the examination of contemporary literature, it is clear that artificial intelligence has a substantial impact on different elements of building operations. These kinds of uses involve evaluating and controlling indoor environmental conditions, optimizing the use of several energy sources in buildings, and improving prediction abilities for forecasting activities. Forecasts involve estimating energy loads, subsystem functioning (e.g., HVAC and lighting), and guaranteeing the structural integrity of buildings [199].

Multiple studies have explored the application of artificial intelligence to enhance interior building environments. Artificial intelligence has been used in research to predict thermal comfort and integrate it with HVAC management techniques to guide control systems. The work employed a blend of machine learning for predicting thermal comfort and reinforcement learning for managing temperature to develop a data-driven HVAC controller centered on comfort. The machine learning comfort model outperformed the PMV model based on the results. Research has also explored optimizing indoor air quality along with thermal comfort. Another study utilized deep reinforcement learning to create an HVAC controller aiming to reduce energy consumption while maintaining optimal thermal comfort and air quality in a university building. The results showed that PMV remained within an appropriate range and also exhibited notable reductions in CO₂ levels and energy consumption compared to standard controllers [200–202].

In addition, regarding AI use in buildings, Occupant Centric Control (OCC) methods are becoming very important. The strategies focus on customizing interior settings by adapting circumstances to suit the comfort requirements of occupants. A new Personal Comfort Model (PCM) has been developed to anticipate occupants' heat feelings and CO₂ intakes. The model has been validated using real experimental data. PCM, when incorporated into building energy simulation tools, allows for the development of sophisticated control algorithms to enhance energy efficiency. Model predictive control (MPC) enhances optimal comfort control by efficiently regulating HVAC systems. The study represents substantial advancements in energy-efficient and occupant-centric building design [203].

Following the discussion on Occupant Centric Control (OCC), recent literature reveals substantial research into artificial intelligence (AI) applications in HVAC systems. Many AI-equipped HVAC systems have been presented commercially, but their different methods and energy-saving results make it difficult for them to be widely accepted. A new analysis method is suggested, which involves integrating a literature review with design thinking utilizing the PRISMA framework. The method combines information from more than 1700 research publications to create artificial intelligence features for energy-efficient HVAC systems. An in-depth analysis was carried out utilizing raw data from 88 research publications to highlight the significance of enhancing hardware alongside AI applications to accomplish substantial energy conservation in different HVAC components [204].

Subsequent to the discourse on OCC and AI applications in HVAC systems, various studies have broadened the scope of AI's function in buildings to enhance energy efficiency and indoor air quality. These studies emphasize various AI-driven approaches utilized in different building components and systems, such as HVAC, envelope optimization, shading structures, and integrated renewable energy systems. The utilization of AI in various domains illustrates its transformative capacity to improve building efficiency, decrease energy usage, and elevate occupant comfort. Table 2 encapsulates crucial case studies that demonstrate AI-driven solutions for enhancing energy efficiency and indoor air quality, offering significant insights into the practical results, techniques, and contributions of contemporary research.

Table 2

Case studies on AI applications for building energy efficiency and indoor air quality.

Authors	Methodology	Key Findings	Contribution
Ahmad et al [205].	Developed an AI-driven optimization instrument for shading buildings with Python and Rhino Grasshopper.	Enhanced façade shading decreased energy usage by 26.2% to 30%.	AI demonstrated its role in retrofitting midrise buildings to improve energy efficiency.
Zhao et al [206].	Integrated resistance-capacitance models and dynamic Bayesian networks for load prediction.	Improved accuracy in cooling and heating load forecasting, achieving a 14.74% decrease in summer errors and a 59.78% reduction in winter errors..	Emphasized AI's capacity to include thermal properties and occupant behavior for load prediction.
Jeong et al [207].	Incorporating PPO into subway ventilation control systems for real-time operations.	Achieved a 22% reduction in energy use while preserving indoor air quality (IAQ).	Demonstrated AI's efficacy in regulating indoor air quality and energy efficiency in intricate environments.
Long [208]	Integrated simulation, machine learning techniques (e.g., Gradient Boosting), and artificial intelligence optimization methods.	Achieved simultaneous reductions in cost and energy during the initial envelope design (7.52% cost reduction, 8.48% energy reduction).	Created AI-driven solutions for energy-efficient building design in the initial design phases.
Shboul et al [209].	Developed a Building Integrated Photovoltaic Thermal (BIPV/T) system utilizing MATLAB/Simulink® for dynamic modeling. Performed techno-economic and sensitivity analysis, artificial neural network prediction, and multi-objective optimization using NSGA-II.	The optimized BIPV/T system attained a net thermal power of 5320 W, an efficiency of 63%, and a minimal footprint of 32.89 m ² . Levelized cost of electricity: \$0.10 per kilowatt-hour.	Validated the practicality of AI-augmented BIPV/T systems for energy efficiency and economic viability in residential buildings.
Ntafalias et al [210].	Created an IoT platform to amalgamate old HVAC and other building systems with machine learning (ML) techniques. Practical demonstrations were executed in Ireland and Greece.	Energy savings Ireland Residential (39%), Commercial (61%) Greece Residential (60%), Commercial (4.6%). Cost reductions Greece 10% monthly residential bill, 22% commercial electricity bill.	Illustrated how the integration of IoT and ML with legacy systems can yield substantial energy savings and cost reductions without necessitating costly equipment upgrades.
Lee et al [211].	Illustrated how the integration of IoT and ML with legacy systems can yield substantial energy savings and cost reductions without necessitating costly equipment upgrades.	The LSTM model attained a prediction accuracy of 60% to 80% for bioaerosols and 90% for particulate matter (PM). Accurate real-time and short-term (<=60 min) forecasts of indoor air quality in commercial office and shopping mall environments.	Demonstrated AI's capability to monitor and forecast indoor bioaerosol levels, improving real-time environmental quality management in high-occupancy public spaces.

In summary, AI technologies substantially enhance indoor conditions and decrease energy usage, both essential for attaining nearly zero Energy Buildings (NZEB). The literature assessment indicates that AI-driven solutions, including enhanced HVAC control, predictive energy modeling, and smart ventilation systems, improve thermal comfort and indoor air quality while maximizing energy economy. These developments highlight the revolutionary capacity of AI in occupant-focused building design and operation. Achieving NZEB objectives necessitates overcoming hurdles such as system integration, cost factors, and user acceptance through a holistic strategy that integrates AI innovations with sustainable design techniques.

4. Gap Study Analysis

The endeavor to achieve nearly zero-Energy Buildings signifies a crucial achievement in the realm of sustainable building design and operation. However, attaining NZEB certification is filled with difficulties, and doing a thorough gap analysis is crucial to identifying the specific areas that are impeding development. As shown in Fig. 13, This section explores the complex difficulties surrounding the achievement of NZEB goals, with a specific emphasis on HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) energy consumption and on-site energy production, particularly in developing nations such as Egypt.

4.1. HVAC Energy Usage

Oversizing; One of the main factors leading to higher energy consumption in buildings is the excessive dimensioning of Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. Oversizing of the systems leads to inefficiency, as they are specifically intended to handle maximum loads, which in turn results in inferior performance under typical circumstances.

4.1.1. Inefficient Building Envelope

The insufficiency of building envelopes, defined by inadequate insulation and air leakage, worsens the energy requirements of HVAC systems. The weak building envelope facilitates the transfer of thermal energy to the outside surroundings, resulting in elevated heating and cooling demands in order to uphold desired inside comfort levels.

4.1.2. Lighting Type

The selection of lighting employed in buildings has a substantial impact on total energy usage. Obsolete and ineffective lighting systems result in increased electricity consumption, which directly affects HVAC needs. Hence, it is crucial to tackle the inefficiencies in lighting systems in order to attain energy neutrality in buildings.

4.2. On-Site Energy Generation

4.2.1. Lack of Renewable Energy Integration

One of the main obstacles to the adoption of NZEB in developing nations like Egypt is the inadequate incorporation of renewable energy sources into on-site energy generation schemes. The dependence on traditional energy sources impedes the advancement toward sustainability objectives, underscoring the necessity for a fundamental change in energy production methods.

4.2.2. Photovoltaic Efficiency

Although photovoltaic (PV) systems are becoming more popular for on-site energy production, outdated views on their effectiveness may not align with current advancements. Previous constraints in PV technology may have limited their effectiveness, but recent advancements have led to significant enhancements in efficiency. Optimizing PV efficiency is essential for maximizing their impact on the energy balance of Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB). Continued progress in PV technology is crucial to improve their efficiency in achieving NZEB goals.

Fig. 13. Gap study analysis.

4.2.3. AI for NZEB

With its ability to optimize energy performance and sustainability, artificial intelligence (AI) might greatly speed up the transition to nearly zero Energy Buildings (NZEB). AI-driven energy prediction models facilitate accurate demand-supply management via sophisticated forecasting and real-time analytics, hence improving energy efficiency. Intelligent building automation systems and optimization algorithms dynamically regulate activities, identify anomalies, and reduce energy waste. AI-driven, occupant-focused controls optimize thermal comfort, air quality, and energy consumption, whereas AI-augmented HVAC systems enhance efficiency via predictive controls and sophisticated hardware integration. Moreover, AI tools enhance diagnostics, fault identification, and facility management, guaranteeing consistent performance. Through the utilization of intelligent sensors and extensive data analytics, AI facilitates the adaptive and efficient operation of buildings, addressing essential gaps in the attainment of the NZEB target.

Addressing issues such as excessive size, enhancing the performance of the building envelope, refining lighting systems, incorporating renewable energy sources, enhancing PV efficiency, and investigating cutting-edge energy storage technologies such as hydrogen are essential steps towards achieving NZEB. Furthermore, utilizing AI can substantially aid in optimizing energy management, advancing building automation, augmenting occupant comfort, and facilitating real-time predictive controls. AI-driven solutions can enhance energy consumption forecasts, optimize HVAC systems, and improve building management; hence, increasing efficiency. Collaborative research and the integration of AI can facilitate the establishment of a sustainable built environment, especially in developing nations such as Egypt.

5. Conclusion and Outcomes

In light of rising global concerns such as pandemics, conflicts, and climate change, the move to sustainable building techniques has become critical. Nearly-zero-Energy Buildings (NZEBs) offer a revolutionary approach by markedly reducing energy usage and greenhouse gas emissions while improving occupant comfort and providing enduring cost benefits. Nonetheless, despite their potential, numerous obstacles remain, especially in developing areas such as the MENA, where economic, infrastructural, and regulatory issues hinder extensive implementation.

This review has illustrated the diverse advantages of NZEBs, encompassing their capacity to preserve energy, enhance indoor environments, and alleviate climate change by decreasing carbon footprints and dependence on renewable energy. Improvements in artificial intelligence (AI), digital twin technology, and energy management systems also offer chances to improve NZEB performance, making these structures more and more possible for achieving energy independence and resilience.

Numerous difficulties persist unresolved in the current literature and practice. Technological integration, including the implementation of modern materials such as phase-change systems and high-performance glass, necessitates additional validation across many climatic conditions, especially in the MENA area. Economic factors provide substantial obstacles, as complete lifecycle cost evaluations are absent, complicating the assessment of financial viability in emerging nations. Furthermore, the lack of strong regulatory frameworks, defined performance metrics, and public awareness hinders the extensive deployment of NZEBs. The lack of data, particularly about regional insights on energy performance, material efficiency, and renewable integration, intensifies these issues.

Targeted recommendations for policymakers, practitioners, and academics are necessary to address these concerns. Policymakers ought to implement financial incentives, including subsidies, tax reductions, and grants, to promote the construction and renovation of NZEBs. Implementing region-specific energy performance standards and promoting

public-private partnerships will expedite adoption. Practitioners must implement integrated design methodologies that prioritize energy efficiency and renewable integration in the conceptual phase, employing AI-driven tools for predictive analytics and adaptive building management. Researchers ought to concentrate on comprehensive case studies, assess the efficacy of modern technologies in real-world scenarios, and investigate hybrid energy solutions that integrate both on-site and off-site renewable sources.

Future technologies, like AIoT, digital twins, and machine learning, present excellent opportunities for the advancement of NZEBs. Digital twins provide real-time surveillance and enhancement of building performance, whereas AIoT improves energy efficiency via predictive maintenance and adaptive controls. Enhanced collaboration throughout the MENA area to exchange best practices and resources would further bolster NZEB implementation. By tackling these difficulties and using emerging technologies, NZEBs can serve as a fundamental element of sustainable urban development, offering scalable and adaptive frameworks to attain global energy and climate objectives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohanad M. Ibrahim: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **María Jose Suarez-Lopez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ahmed A. Hanafy:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Micheal A. William:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

As a review article, all references used are well cited using in-text citations.

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